

The *Lorscher Arzneibuch*

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Abstract

The *Lorscher Arzneibuch* (LA), also *Lorsch Pharmacopoeia* or *Lorsch Book of Remedies*, is the earliest surviving medical compendium from the Frankish–German world, produced in the Lorsch scriptorium and usually dated to the late eighth or early ninth century. Conceived as a practical handbook, it combines a protreptic defence of medicine, isagogic pieces, capitulationes with short recipes, synonym and substitution lists, dietetic notes, and, at the end, Anthimus' *Observatio ciborum*. With 482 recipes preserved after substantial leaf losses, the original extent must have approached seven hundred or more items. The work condenses late-antique and early-medieval Latin material into a Carolingian monastic frame and is now a primary witness for the formation of learned medicine north of the Alps. Its inscription on UNESCO's Memory of the World Register in 2013 reflects its cultural weight; pharmacological claims are to be handled cautiously and kept within the philological evidence.

Keywords: *Lorscher Arzneibuch*; *Lorsch Pharmacopoeia*; *Lorsch Book of Remedies*; monastic medicine; Carolingian medicine; recipe compendia; *Medicina Plinii*; *Physica Plinii*; Anthimus; codicology; herbal medicine

Manuscript and transmission history

The manuscript now preserved at the Bamberg State Library under the shelfmark Msc. Med. 1 is the oldest surviving witness of monastic medicine in the Franconian-German region. The codex has been kept in Bamberg for more than 1,000 years and was produced around the year 800 [Niedenthal 2022]. On palaeographical grounds, it is attributed to the scriptorium of the imperial abbey of Lorsch. The dating to the late eighth or early ninth century has been established since Bischoff's studies [Bischoff 1998] and is supported by codicological evidence [Stoll 1990]. The codex consists of 75 parchment leaves of partly differing quality. The script in early Carolingian minuscule shows rubricated section openings and segmented sequences of recipes [Stoll 1992]. Quires, rubrication, and marginal notes attest an active use over a long period [UB Heidelberg 2014/2022]. Its inclusion in UNESCO's Memory of the World Register in June 2013 underscores the codex's cultural-historical significance for the transition of ancient medicine into the Middle Ages [Niedenthal 2022]. The manuscript probably reached Bamberg as a donation by Emperor Henry II on the occasion of the foundation of the bishopric in 1007.

Political and cultural background

The monastery of Lorsch was founded around 764 and transferred to Charlemagne in 772. It held a central position within Carolingian educational and reform policy. Lorsch functioned as a politico-religious centre and an important site of book culture. Between its foundation and the end of Carolingian rule, the monastery attained an uncommon cultural flourishing [Scheffers 1998]. The emergence of the LA falls within the epoch of Carolingian renewal, in which medicine enjoyed a high status at court. Einhard reports in the *Vita Karoli Magni* on the emperor's relationship with his physicians. He writes that Charlemagne almost hated the medical men because they urged him to forgo roasted meat in favour of boiled food (*Vita Karoli* c. 22). The promotion of the healing arts formed part of the programme to educate and consolidate the realm. A direct derivation of the contents from royal capitularies remains disputed in scholarship, since explicit source evidence is lacking [Fischer 2010]. More recent research tends to view Lorsch primarily as a place of compilation and copying rather than as the place of original composition for all texts contained in the codex [Fischer 2025].

The justification of the healing art

The codex opens with the *Defensio medicinae*, a programmatic justification of the healing art. Since Sudhoff's work, this text has been treated as an independent witness that helped to secure the acceptance of medicine in a monastic context [Sudhoff 1913]. The anonymous author deploys an argumentative chain to defend the healing art against theological objections. He grounds the compatibility of Christian faith and secular medicine in the claim that remedies are part of God's creation. He writes that God created medicine in order to assist human weakness [Gamble 2020]. The text addresses patients with regard to the spiritual significance of illness and calls on caregivers to practise charity.

As a model it cites the biblical word that a cup of cold water given in Christ's name will be repaid (Matt. 10, 42). The *Defensio* draws on patristic authors; dependencies have been identified on Cassiodor's *Institutiones* (Inst. 1, 31), Isidor's *Differentiae* and *Sententiae*, as well as works by Gregory the Great and Jerome [Gamble 2020]. It is pointed out that Hippocrates' texts on herbs and cures as well as works by Galen and Caelius Aurelianus should be read (Inst. 1, 31, 78). The attribution of the *Defensio* to Abbot Richbod of Lorsch is critically questioned in scholarship, since unambiguous linguistic evidence is lacking [Fischer 2025].

Structure of the recipe corpus and dietetics

The introductory apology is followed by isagogic pieces and an extensive collection of recipes. These are arranged partly by disease patterns and partly by forms of application. The LA contains *capitulationes* with short recipes, lists of synonyms, and dietetic sections. The final item is Anthimus' treatise *Observatio ciborum*. The compilation is tailored to practical care within a monastery [Stoll 1990].

Of the originally probably 700 to 750 recipes, only 482 survive owing to substantial losses of leaves. Gaps occur after fols. 10, 18, 23, 27, 31, and 50 [Stoll 1992]. The recipes address gastrointestinal disorders, fevers, and eye diseases. A poem appended to the work additionally differentiates treatment by the patient's social status. The author writes that for the rich there is a just opportunity for gains, whereas for the poor a single reward suffices [Fischer 2025]. The dietetic concepts are oriented towards the late antique tradition.

Important medicinal and spice drugs

Alongside many drugs still in use today, the LA also includes animal components from the late antique tradition. Thus, for incipient gout the patient is to place his feet into the opened body of a donkey that has first been fattened and then freshly slaughtered, in order to use its warmth (II, 146). A mouse rubbed with oil is said to help against pain in the ankle joints (II, 122), and the application of a living, torn mouse is meant to help when extracting foreign bodies (II, 182).

Absinthium (wormwood)

Wormwood is cited chiefly for stomach and digestive complaints such as a cold stomach or diarrhoea. Externally, the plant is used in ointments against ulcers, with a poultice in combination with aloe mentioned among other remedies (I, 9). In addition, wormwood is a component of ointments against lower-leg ulcers and gout (I, 35). For gastric ailments it is often combined with dill (II, 72) or applied as a mash poultice with rose oil (II, 73). A wormwood oxymel is used to treat stomach pain, intermittent fever, and excess phlegm (II, 198). Galen's recipe against gastric upset and swelling of the liver (II, 217) contains, besides wormwood, aloe, mastic, and wild vine sap. Further indications include flux of the belly (II, 217), splenic disorders (V, 60), nausea (V, 19), and shortness of breath (V, 1, 35). Wormwood is also a fixed ingredient of complex antidotes such as the three-pepper electuary or the panacea (V, 75). Against haematomas ("blue bruises") it is recommended in recipe I, 5c, and a juice against poisons appears under II, 238. A special poultice against a chilled stomach lists, besides wormwood, aloe and Indian nard (V, 35c).

Agaricum (larch polypore or honey fungus)

Stoll identifies the drug in the *Arzneibuch* as larch polypore (*Polyporus officinalis*), while noting that identification as honey fungus represents a misinterpretation in older work. Agaricum is often a component of "wonder remedies", such as the Great Holy Remedy after Galen (II, 21) or the God's Gift (II, 36). In recipe I, 7 the drug is combined in pills against scabies with aloe and mastic. It is used under I, 30c for disorders of the stomach, spleen, and kidneys as well as for dropsy. Agaricum is also an ingredient of purgative pills (I, 39) and remedies against glanders (II, 215). In the God's Gift against kidney disease (V, 41) it constitutes the principal component. Further indications are chronic ailments, melancholy (V, 49), and childhood diseases such as measles or chickenpox (I, 83). Dissolved in wormwood wine, agaricum is recommended for head and liver pain (V, 11).

In the *Antidotum Anacardium* (V, 26), agaricum is likewise listed for patients with stomach complaints and asthma. A holy remedy of the *Logodion* (V, 49) serves to cleanse the body.

Aloe (Aloe vera)

Aloe is among the most frequently mentioned plants, with the liver-coloured quality (aloe hepatices) often specified. Its use concentrates on the gastrointestinal tract and purgative processes. Aloe is an ingredient of pills against scabies (I, 7) and special purgative ointments (I, 10). For headaches it is rubbed in mixed with vinegar (II, 3). In ophthalmology it is used to treat visual weakness and leucomas (II, 209; II, 214). Against halitosis resulting from gastric upset, aloe is prescribed in recipe II, 228. In complex antidotes such as the *God's Gift* (V, 41), it is often the principal component, in a quantity of 60 drachms. Under V, 3b a "health remedy" (*Antidotum eia*) with 10 ounces (80 drachms) of aloe is listed against liver and kidney disorders. A plaster against stomach pain and swelling of the liver includes aloe under II, 226. Against retching, a poultice with myrrh and mastic is applied to the stomach region (II, 249).

Anethum (dill)

Dill is used for disorders of the stomach, digestion, and lungs. It is mentioned for consumption (II, 257; II, 260) as well as angina (II, 50). It is also a component of healing drinks against spots in the eyes (I, 11) and to reduce fever (I, 63). To warm the stomach, dill is named twice under II, 72b. Against swelling of the stomach, the LA recommends a poultice (III, 61). Anthimus describes dill, together with celery and coriander, as an obligatory addition in food preparation (Anthimus, c. 83). Further uses occur for lumbago (II, 118) and in a purgative against phlegm (I, 66b).

Anisum (anise)

Anise is never listed as a single drug (*simplicium*), but always in combination with other substances. The fields of use concern primarily digestion and the respiratory tract. It is a component of the "saving remedy" (I, 47) as well as of an oxymel for cleansing liver, spleen, and kidneys (II, 210). For shortness of breath and "chest wheezing" it is recommended under II, 223. Anise has an analgesic effect in abdominal cramps and side pain (III, 24). In the *Antidotum Pallas* (V, 1, 23) it serves in the treatment of poisoning and animal bites. As a principal component, anise appears in remedies against melancholy (I, 66d) as well as in a recipe for an "immortality remedy" (V, 1, 11).

Apium (celery, eppich)

Celery is one of the central plants of monastic medicine. Its dissolving properties are emphasised, in particular for dribbling of urine, stones, cough, and to promote menstruation. The LA also stresses that celery lifts the mood (III, 47). It is the principal component of the "saving remedy" (I, 47) in a dosage of 20 drachms. Further indications include palpitations (III, 1), liver disorders (III, 38), and dropsy (I, 88). In combination with fenugreek it is prescribed for disorders of the spleen (V, 1, 51). A Hadrian remedy lists celery under III, 37b, while a powder under I, 92 is recommended against urinary stones.

Asarum (hazelwort)

Hazelwort is used as a dissolving remedy for the "softening of the belly" (I, 2; I, 31) and for respiratory complaints. It also helps with joint pain, gout, and paralytic symptoms (V, 32). Hazelwort is found in almost all major compound remedies, such as the immortality remedy (V, 1, 11) or the *God's Gift* (I, 67). Under II, 227 the root is prescribed for swelling of the liver and kidney pain. A "divine remedy" (III, 35) uses hazelwort to treat stomach complaints and fever.

Cardamomum (cardamom)

Cardamom displays a broad spectrum of indications in the LA and is frequently present in the codex's major recipes. The drug is used in antidotes against deadly poisons (I, 29g) as well as in the treatment of dropsy (II, 145). For skin diseases such as leprosy, cardamom is listed under II, 176b. The Hadrian remedy (III, 37) likewise employs the drug, as does a poultice for stomach, spleen, and liver in which cardamom appears as the first named ingredient (I, 52). In important remedies such as the *God's Gift* (V, 1, 16) or the three-pepper electuary (V, 1, 18; V, 1, 19), cardamom is regularly present. In the *Antidotum Pallas* it also serves to treat headaches (V, 1, 23; V, 1, 24). Further applications include shortness of breath and gout.

Caryophyllon (clove)

Clove is described chiefly as a dissolving remedy. Its fields of use include urinary stones, gastric and intestinal complaints, and disorders of the womb. A corresponding remedy against white spots in the eye is listed under I, 11. Caryophyllon also appears in antidotes against poisons (I, 29b). For urinary stones, a clove powder in wine is used (II, 105). Headaches and vertigo are treated under II, 197. In a "clearing drink" for the winter half-year, clove is a fixed component of the recipe (II, 218). Further

indications include palpitations (III, 1) and shortness of breath (III, 20). The Antidotum Anacardium (V, 26) also lists clove as a component for stomach complaints and asthma.

Cassia / Cinnamomum (cinnamon / cassia cinnamon)

Cinnamon is listed under the names cassia and cinnamomum. The drug is a component of numerous health-promoting recipes (II, 235). It appears in the Great Remedy (II, 21) and in the God's Gift (II, 22), to which a preventive effect is ascribed. Under II, 58 cassia is included in a tooth powder, and it is also listed in the three-pepper electuary (II, 60).

Centaurea (centaury)

Centaury is used for headache, fever, and gastrointestinal complaints. It serves as an anthelmintic (I, 45c) and to treat dysentery (II, 91). In the theriac recipe (V, 1, 30) it is used for the falling sickness (epilepsy) and gout. For limb pain, Centaurea is regarded as the main remedy (V, 36). Against nausea it is designated under the synonym *fel terrae* ("earth gall") (II, 69). Further indications are scorpion stings (II, 189) and respiratory complaints (II, 208). A urinary stone remedy lists Centaurea in combination with lovage wine (II, 105).

Cuminum (cumin)

Cumin is used primarily for stomach pain (I, 30, I, 38) and to promote digestion (II, 74; II, 75; II, 77). It is a component of numerous complex recipes against flatulence and abdominal pain (I, 52; I, 54; I, 58). Under II, 240 cumin, in combination with pepper and eppich seed, is prescribed against catarrh.

Euphorbeum (spurge)

Spurge is used for protection against poisons in complex recipes (I, 37). Further indications include lumbago (II, 61), sciatica (II, 118b), "hip pain" (II, 62; II, 119), and dropsy (II, 63; II, 145). For a "cold stomach" euphorbeum is recommended in recipes II, 77 and II, 224. It also appears in Galen's holy remedy (II, 21) and in the Antidotum of Philon (II, 30b; II, 89).

Feniculum (fennel)

Fennel is among the most frequently mentioned plants. In recipe II, 71 fennel seed is used against stomach pain. In combination with celery, parsley, and lovage it serves as an anthelmintic (I, 45e). The bark of the fennel root is recommended together with aloe and vinegar against a chilled stomach (II, 3). Against "black bile", fennel is combined with eppich (II, 91). A purgative drink lists fennel alongside eppich and rue (II, 259).

Fenum graecum (fenugreek)

Fenugreek is used for cough (II, 51; II, 58), to strengthen the stomach (II, 54; II, 73), and for dropsy (II, 63; II, 145). Externally it is used to treat inguinal hernias (II, 60; II, 115) as well as swellings (II, 65). It is also prescribed for swelling of the liver (II, 78; II, 227). Under V, 1, 51 fenugreek is recommended together with eppich seed for disorders of the spleen.

Marrubium (horehound)

Although the LA lacks a strict scheme of indications for horehound, inflammation, cough, and digestive complaints are in focus. It is used for scabies and itch (I, 4b), as an enema against phlegm (I, 37), and to strengthen the teeth in water (II, 36). Against chronic cough, horehound is combined with hyssop, ginger, and honey (II, 58). Externally it is used to treat skin spots, leprosy (II, 176), and dog bites (II, 184). It appears in an antidote against anxiety states and palpitations (V, 27) as well as in electuaries against cough (V, 18). To cleanse the head and strengthen the stomach, horehound is recommended under III, 40.

Piper (pepper)

Pepper is usually listed in the forms black pepper (*Piper nigrum*) and long pepper (*P. longum*). It is the eponymous component of the important three-pepper electuary (Diatrionpiperion, V, 60), which is used for disorders of the stomach, spleen, and kidneys. In Galenic theory, pepper serves to generate heat and dryness in order to dissolve excess, cold phlegm. It is also used against catarrh in combination with cumin and eppich seed (II, 240) and in healing drinks against cough (II, 248).

Plantago (plantain)

Plantain is mentioned relatively frequently in the codex (I, 29; I, 31; I, 34). The pressed juice (*succus*) serves to treat worm infestation (I, 45a). Further applications are found in I, 42 and I, 47. The leaves are used under I, 67. In identification, it is usually assumed to be broadleaf plantain (*Plantago major*) or ribwort plantain (*P. lanceolata*).

Pyrethrum (pellitory)

Pellitory is used against poisons (II, 29b), thirst (I, 40; II, 36), and catarrh (I, 45; II, 2; II, 193; II, 241). Further indications include lumbago and hip pain (II, 61; II, 62; II, 118) as well as reducing swelling of the uvula (II, 83; II, 256). In recipe II, 71 pellitory is also prescribed for stomach pain.

Zingiber (ginger)

Ginger is one of the most important drugs in the LA and is used in more than 50 recipes. Its application concentrates on warming the digestive tract and treating diseases of the respiratory tract. According to Galenic qualitative theory, the plant is classified as “warm and dry in the third degree”. Against chronic cough, ginger is prescribed in combination with horehound, hyssop, and honey (II, 58). In complex electuaries and antidotes, its pungency serves to stimulate the body's own heat and to dissolve tenacious phlegm. It is often used together with black and long pepper for the three-pepper electuary (diapiperon) (V, 60). Ginger is also a component of the Hadrian remedy (III, 37) and the immortality remedy (V, 1, 11). In the *Antidotum Pallas* (V, 1, 23) it is used for poisonings and animal bites; as a digestive aid it is mentioned under I, 31. Its wide distribution shows that ginger, despite its exotic origin, was regarded in early medieval Lorsch as an indispensable therapeutic, among other places in the *Antidotum Anacardium* (V, 26).

Philological analysis and technical-linguistic findings

The linguistic form of the LA is characterised by late Latin features. The text shows influences of the vernacular and a Latinisation of Greek technical terms [Önnerfors 1992]. On fols. 6v to 7v the *Problemata quae dicuntur Aristotelis* are found, which are considered interpretatively delicate. The compiler uses terms such as *pigmentaria* for the pharmacy or the drug stock. Önnerfors offers detailed word studies of terms such as *scofella* and *malagma*. He writes that *scofella* is a vernacular variant of *scrofulae* and denotes a swelling at the neck. *Malagma* is described as a softening plaster that frequently occurs in late antique recipe literature. The term *cataplasma* is also discussed and identified as a poultice. These features show that the LA was a practical text for monastic use [Önnerfors 1992]. Önnerfors stresses the importance of philological control in order to avoid misinterpretations, as in the case of *quiparum*. He also points to morphological peculiarities that are typical of the transition from Late Latin to early Medieval Latin.

Medical-historical classification and controversies

Since the late twentieth century, the codex has received increased public attention, which in part has led to anachronistic interpretations. Claims concerning the use of penicillin or cardiac glycosides in the early Middle Ages are rejected in the field as not robust. The author notes that such readings are time-bound and do not withstand text-critical verification [Fischer 2010]. Scholarship warns against equating historical applications directly with modern substance concepts such as acetylcholinesterase inhibition without taking account of the philological textual basis [Önnerfors 1992]. The *Arzneibuch* is regarded as a principal witness of Carolingian medicine, yet pharmacological retro-projections are cautioned against. Questions concerning scribal hands, later layers of use, and the precise origin of individual texts remain subjects of ongoing investigation [Stoll 1990]. Fischer questions the attribution of the *Defensio* to Richbod of Lorsch and notes the absence of linguistic evidence [Fischer 2025].

Reception and afterlife

The LA thus documents a phase in which medical knowledge of antiquity was secured within a Christian framework and laid the foundation for later Western healing practice. In later centuries, the contents of monastic medicine were often incorporated anonymously into herbals. Works of monastic medicine were still printed in the fifteenth and early sixteenth centuries. Plant applications survived primarily through inclusion in successful herbals such as the *Gart der Gesundheit*. A serious scholarly engagement with this epoch is only recorded again from the second half of the twentieth century [Niedenthal 2022].

The most recent work of the CEMLM project has more than doubled the number of known early medieval medical manuscripts to approximately 475 witnesses (van Rhijn et al. 2025). These finds, mostly marginal recipes and single entries in non-medical codices, nonetheless rather underscore the special status of the LA. Among the newly identified sources, no second example has yet been found of a comparably structured compendium with a programmatic introduction, systematic ordering of recipes, and a dietetic concluding text.

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DE Kurzabstract: Das Lorscher Arzneibuch (LA) gilt als das früheste erhaltene medizinische Kompendium aus dem fränkisch-deutschen Raum und wird paläographisch in das späte 8./frühe 9. Jahrhundert datiert. Als praxisorientiertes Handbuch vereint es Proömien, Einführungsstücke, kurze Rezeptkapitel (capitulationes), Synonym-/Substitutionslisten, Diätetik sowie am Schluss Anthimus' *Observatio ciborum*. Nach erheblichen Blattverlusten sind 482 Rezepte erhalten; der ursprüngliche Umfang dürfte deutlich darüber gelegen haben. Das LA bündelt spätantike und frühmittelalterliche lateinische Überlieferungen in einem karolingischen, monastischen Rahmen und ist ein Schlüsselzeugnis für die Formierung gelehrter Medizin nördlich der Alpen.

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